

PYRAZOLE DERIVATIVES.

BY TRJENDRA NATH GHOSH AND DEBABRATA DAS-GUPTA.

An indolylpyrazolone derivative has been synthesised. The syntheses of some pyrrolopyrazole and dipyrazole derivatives have been described.

The synthesis of pyrroloquinol has been described by Mrs. Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2948) and of pyrrolyndoles by Aggarwal, Qureshi and Ray (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 3988). In view of the fact that some pyrazolone derivatives (*e.g.* antipyrine, amidopyrine, etc.) exhibit pronounced antipyretic properties, it seemed of interest to synthesise some indolylpyrazolone derivatives.

3-Carboxyiminino-4-acetylphenylhydrazone-1-phenylpyrazolone (Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 87) could not be successfully made to undergo the Fischer indole transformation. However, the phenylhydrazone (I) of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-acetylpyrazolone has now been transformed to α -indolyl pyrazolone derivative (II) with zinc chloride. Alcoholic hydrochloric acid transforms the compound (I) to the dipyrazole derivative (III). This indicates that phenylhydrazone derivatives of the type (I) require drastic conditions for conversion into indoles (*cf.* Brunck, *Annalen*, 1893, **272**, 201; Ray *et al.*, *loc. cit.*; Mumm and Petzold, *Annalen*, 1938, **536**, 23).

(I)

(II)

(III)

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-aminopyrazolone condenses with acetylacetone to furnish the pyrrolopyrazole derivative (IV) (*cf.* Duden, *Annalen*, 1900, 318, 25; Dohrn and Thiele, *Ber.*, 1931, 64, 2863). The compound (IV) reacts with benzaldehyde to give a chalkone.

EXPERIMENTAL.

3-Methyl-4-acetylphenylhydrazone-1-phenylpyrazolone (I), prepared by adding an equimolecular proportion of phenylhydrazine to an alcoholic solution of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-acetylpyrazolone (Stolz, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1897, 55, 154), was crystallised from alcohol in colourless slender needles, m.p. 197°.

4-*α*-Indolyl-1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone (II).—An intimate mixture of the compound (I, 12 g.) and anhydrous zinc chloride (50 g.) was heated at 200° for 3 hours. The product was cooled, powdered and thoroughly washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and hot water. The solid obtained was found to contain zinc. It was, therefore, kept in contact with cold concentrated hydrochloric acid for about 1 hour and filtered. The clear acid solution, on dilution with water, gave a brown pasty mass which, however, could not be purified. The insoluble portion was extracted with glacial acetic acid; the solution, on dilution with water, furnished a solid (3 g.) which was further purified by dissolving in cold dilute alkali and precipitating with hydrochloric acid. It was finally crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in colourless shining rectangular plates and dried at 140°, m. p. 238° (decomp., shrinking at 225°). (Found: C, 74.42; H, 5.28; N, 14.27. C₁₈H₁₅ON₃ requires C, 74.74; H, 5.19; N, 14.53 per cent). It is readily soluble in cold dilute alkali, from which it is precipitated by acid as a white flocculent mass. Its alcoholic solution gives a red colouration with ferric chloride. A solution of the substance in concentrated sulphuric acid gives a deep green colour with alloxan. With isatin and sulphuric acid the red colour, slowly changes to deep violet. If a minute quantity of the substance is added to an alcoholic solution

of a small quantity of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde and 2-3 drops of dilute hydrochloric acid, and the solution is boiled for about 5 minutes and cooled, a light pink colour is developed. If to this solution 2 drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid are now added and the solution heated for about 1 minute, the colour changes to light green.

1:1'-*Diphenyl-3:3'-dimethyl-(4:5:4':5')-dipyrazole* (III).—The compound (1.6 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (50 c. c.), saturated with dry hydrogen chloride, when a hydrochloride was deposited as a voluminous precipitate. The hydrochloride went into solution on heating for 6 hours. Alcohol was removed in *vacuo* and the product treated with sodium carbonate solution, when a pasty mass was obtained which soon solidified. The brown solid (3.5 g.) was first crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and water, and then from hot water (charcoal) in colourless rectangular plates, m. p. 129-30° (softening at 123°). (Found : C, 70.27 ; H, 6.42 ; N, 18.13, 18.33; H₂O, 5.42. C₁₈H₁₆N₄, H₂O requires C, 70.59 ; H, 5.88 ; N, 18.30; H₂O, 5.88 per cent). The molecule of water is tenaciously held and only removed completely, when the substance is heated at 140-142° in vacuum. After melting, the substance remains as a colourless syrupy mass, which does not solidify even on standing for several days.

Whereas the compound (I) is soluble* in cold dilute alkali and gives a deep red colouration with ferric chloride, the substance (III) is insoluble in alkali and does not give any colouration with ferric chloride. It is soluble in cold concentrated hydrochloric acid and is not precipitated on dilution with water. The acid solution, on evaporation under reduced pressure, gave a syrupy mass soluble in cold water, which did not solidify even on long standing in vacuum. The hydrochloride is soluble in alcohol and is precipitated as an oil by addition of ether. The substance (III) does not contain any diazotisable amino group.

1-*Phenyl-3-methyl-4:5-(2'-methyl-3'-acetopyrrolo) (4':5')-pyrazole* (IV).—To a glacial acetic acid solution of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-aminopyrazolone, prepared according to Knorr (*Annalen*, 1887, 238, 158, 189) an equimolecular proportion of acetylacetone was added and the solution was heated on the water-bath for about 6 hours. The solution, which was orange-coloured at the beginning turned deep red on heating. It was cooled and diluted with water, when a reddish brown solid separated which was washed with alcohol and ether. It is practically insoluble in hot alcohol and crystallised from large quantity of glacial acetic acid in colourless rectangular plates, m. p. above 320°, yield about 5%.

(Found: C, 70'82; H, 6'33, N, 16'49. $C_{12}H_{15}ON_3$, requires C, 71'14; H, 5'92; N, 16'60 per cent). It is readily soluble in cold dilute alkali and precipitated by acid. Its solution in glacial acetic acid does not give any colouration with ferric chloride. With cold concentrated hydrochloric acid it forms the hydrochloride as colourless powder, which is readily hydrolysed by water. With concentrated sulphuric acid the substance turns red and a dark-coloured solution is obtained. A minute quantity of the substance in an alcoholic solution of traces of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde and 2-3 drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid, gave on heating a pale yellow clear solution which when cooled and treated with sodium nitrate, developed a fine bluish green colour.

The yield of the compound (IV) was increased to about 10% by carrying out the above reaction in glacial acetic acid in presence of hydrogen.

The benzylidene derivative was obtained by heating the above substance for 2-3 hours with equimolecular proportion of benzaldehyde in alcoholic solution containing the requisite quantity of alkali. The solution was cooled and acidified with cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The solid, thus obtained, crystallised from acetic acid in colourless rectangular plates, m. p. above 300°. (Found: N, 12'45. $C_{22}H_{19}ON_3$, requires N. 12'31 per cent). It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid to give a deep green solution.

The authors' grateful thanks are due to Professor P. C. Guha for his kind interest in this investigation.

DEPARTMENT OF ORGANIC CHEMISTRY,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BANGALORE

Received January 13, 1939